

On the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) on the island of Madeira (Portugal)

Torsten van der Heyden

Immenweide 83, D-22523 Hamburg, Germany.

E-Mail: tmvdh@web.de ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4138-7160

ABSTRACT: The presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) on the island of Madeira (Portugal) is reported. The known distribution of the species in North Africa is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Zelus renardii*, invasive species, distribution, Madeira, Portugal.

In North Africa, the invasive Nearctic assassin bug species *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) has been reported from the following islands of the Canary archipelago (Spain): Tenerife (Baena & Santos, 2021; van der Heyden, 2022), Lanzarote (van der Heyden, 2023a), Fuerteventura (van der Heyden, 2023b), Gran Canaria (van der Heyden, 2023c) and La Gomera (van der Heyden, 2025). Furthermore, the species is present in Algeria (van der Heyden, 2023d).

Zelus renardii is present on the island of Madeira (Portugal), too: On 07.04.2026, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was found in a flower bed in Funchal (coordinates: 32.6467983, -16.9054), the capital of the island located at its southern coast. Two photos of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Pocius, 2026).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Funchal, Madeira, Portugal, 07.04.2026. (Photo: Tomas Pocius).

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REFERENCES

- Baena, M., Santos, S., 2021, *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, primera cita en las Islas Canarias (Hemiptera, Reduviidae), *Revista gaditana de Entomología*, XII: 131-135.
- Pocius, T., 2026, Leafhopper Assassin Bug (*Zelus renardii*). Photographs to be found on iNaturalist [Online database]. Available from: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/348130812>. (Accessed: 08.04.2026).
- van der Heyden, T., 2022, Confirmation of the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) on the Canary Islands (Spain), *Archivos Entomológicos*, 25: 51.
- van der Heyden, T., 2023a, New records of Heteroptera from the Canary Islands (Spain), IV, *Archivos Entomológicos*, 26: 183-184.
- van der Heyden, T., 2023b, New records of Heteroptera from the Canary Islands (Spain), VI, *Archivos Entomológicos*, 27: 27-28.
- van der Heyden, T., 2023c, New records of Heteroptera from the Canary Islands (Spain), VII, *Archivos Entomológicos*, 27: 81-82.
- van der Heyden, T., 2023d, On the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Algeria, *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 17: 99-100.
- van der Heyden, T., 2025, New records of Heteroptera from the Canary Islands (Spain), XVII, *Archivos Entomológicos*, 32: 231-232.